

Use of microplot technique to evaluate the effect of herbicide and organic fertilizer on dehydrogenase activity in lowland rice soil

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Assessment of soil microbial activity is necessary to understand the nutrient fluxes in a given ecosystem. Soil dehydrogenase activity is one of the measures of microbial activity of a large part of the microbial community in the soil (Alef 1995). In this study, we used a microplot technique to evaluate the effect of herbicide and organic fertilizer application on soil dehydrogenase activity based on the microbial electron transport system (ETS) activity assay.

Two experiments were conducted at PhilRice (longitude 120°56'E; latitude 15°45'N) in November and December 2001 in Maligaya clay soil. Microplots (2 × 2 m) were constructed in a well-puddled soil. The treatments for Experiment 1 were with and without herbicide application (cyhalofop butyl) at 1 L ha⁻¹. For Experiment 2, the treatments were a control (no application), application of 60-40-40 kg NPK ha⁻¹, and 5 t organic fertilizer ha⁻¹. The organic fertilizer contained 0.147% N, 0.152% P, and 8.45% K.

In each experiment, the treatments were replicated four times and laid out in a randomized complete block design. Soil samples (0–15 cm) were collected from the mixture of five random sites in each plot at 0, 2, 4, 6, and 8 d after herbicide application (Experiment 1) and at 1, 10, and 20 d after fertilizer application

(Experiment 2) using a PVC (30-cm length, 15-cm diameter) sampler. The ETS activity assay was done by mixing 0.5 g of homogenized soil sample, 2 mL 0.1 M Tris-HCL buffer (pH 7.7), and 1 mL idonitrophenyltetrazolium (INT) solutions and incubating the mixture for 15 min at 30 °C. The reaction was determined by adding 0.5 mL of 37% formaldehyde. The tubes were centrifuged at 3,000 xg for 15 min. The photometric absorbance of the supernatant was read at 480 nm (IRRI 1998). Statistical analysis and comparison of means were done using IRRISTAT for Windows software.

In Experiment 1, microbial activity in microplots without herbicides was lower than in those with herbicides at 2 and 4 d after application (DAA). However, herbicides had no significant effect on microbial activity at 6 and 8 DAA (Fig. 1). These results indicate that the application of cyhalofop butyl induced a

short-term stimulation of microbial activity in lowland Maligaya clay soil. The increase in microbial activity could be attributed to the rapid degradation of cyhalofop butyl (<http://cdpr/ca.gov/docs/publicreports/5748.pdf>) into organic compounds that may become carbon and energy sources for the microorganisms. Although the result of this study implies that the herbicide could be relatively safe for nontarget organisms in the soil, the effect of continuous application of this pesticide needs further study.

In Experiment 2, organic fertilizer increased microbial activity at 10 and 20 DAA. Moreover, microbial activity in plots with inorganic fertilizer (60-40-40) did not differ from that in untreated plots (Fig. 2). The increase in microbial activity may be one of the causes of the significant increase in rice yield when the soil was treated with the same source of organic fertilizer in a previous

Fig. 1. Dehydrogenase activity in lowland rice soil as affected by application of herbicide cyhalofop butyl. PhilRice, Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, November 2001.

Fig. 2. Soil dehydrogenase activity in microplot as affected by fertilizer application. PhilRice, Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, December 2001.

study. This organic fertilizer was produced from kitchen garbage, crop residues, and tree trimmings that were rapidly decomposed by applying effective microorganism inoculants.

Ecotoxicological studies conducted at PhilRice are done in bigger plots that require more inputs. The treatment application is

also difficult. This is our first attempt to use the microplot method and it minimized our problems in using bigger plots. However, this study will be repeated on planted plots to be able to relate the changes in microbial activity to nutrient availability and rice yield.

References

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IRRI launches first children's storybook

"Graindell" is a children's storybook published by the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI). Written by renowned Filipino children's author Rene O. Villanueva, the book captures the organization's goal for all the children of the world—a "home for tomorrow," a progressive community where no one will go hungry. Through this first title in a series of children's publications, IRRI introduces its future stakeholders to important issues relating to rice, "the grain of life," food to half the world's population, especially in Asia.

Graindell, "the planetoid shaped like a little eye," tells the story of two friends, Abu and Thor, who share a common dream—to turn their home into the greatest place to live. The simple, yet moving, tale comes alive with the masterful renderings of Redge Abos, a young and talented artist from *Ilustrador ng Kabataan* (INK), in watercolor, combined with digital technology.

With the release of this first children's storybook, IRRI launches the "Graindell Community," which espouses the call for a dynamic, well-developed countryside through multisectoral participation. Membership is open to children and their stewards, including parents, teachers, scientists, children's storywriters and illustrators, and other concerned citizens.

The members of the "Graindell Community" converge at the educational Web site, Graindell.com, where IRRI's own scientists lend their expertise to build a popular knowledge bank on rice, against the backdrop of science, food and nutrition, environment, arts and culture, literacy, and community participation. The site teaches children to "aspire, persevere, and achieve" through games, instructional materials, and interactive learning exercises with other children, as well as their stewards.

Graindell is IRRI's first project for the United Nations International Year of Rice to be celebrated in 2004.

The story of "Graindell" celebrates what IRRI is all about. It portrays the organization's endeavor to create a new generation of rice farmers and consumers who will embrace the traditional wisdom of farm life, understand the need for new and creative technology, and work together for a self-sufficient and well-developed society. By involving children now, they can march fearlessly into the future, knowing that "a home for tomorrow" is not only possible—it is achievable.

The "Graindell Community," the book, and the Web site were launched during National Children's Book Day, on July 15, at Museo Pambata in Roxas Boulevard, Manila, spearheaded by the Philippine Board on Books for Young People (PBBY) to promote international understanding through children's literature.

Please visit www.graindell.com <<http://www.graindell.com>> to sign up, get more information, and contribute content to the site.